
Availability and Relevance of Vocational Subjects for Male and Female Students in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Imo State

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Abstract

The study examined availability and relevance of vocational subjects for male and female students in public senior secondary schools in Imo state. Two research questions guided the study and four hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted descriptive research design. The population of the study was 296 public senior secondary schools in Imo state. The sample size was 376 teachers drawn from a population of 6,270 using disproportionate stratified random sampling technique, in the 296 public secondary schools who participated in the study. Self-structured questionnaire designed by the researcher titled: Availability and Relevance of Vocational Subjects for Male and Female Students in Public Secondary Schools Questionnaire (ARVSMFSPSSQ). The reliability of the instrument was gotten using Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient which yielded a reliability index of 0.84 and 0.65. Therefore, the overall reliability index yielded 0.72. Data were analysed using mean and standard deviation and z-test for hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study show that the level of students' interest in vocational education in secondary schools in Imo state was low. While secondary and higher level are not part of it, the available vocational skills in secondary schools in Imo State are practical agriculture, business studies, home economics, local craft, cultural and creative art and the relevance of vocational skill subjects in secondary schools in Imo state. The study concluded that vocational skills taught at the secondary school level in Imo State empower students to be creative. It was recommended among others that the government should come up with plans and innovations to enhance the available vocational skills in secondary schools.

Keywords: Vocational Education, Gender and Education, Curriculum Availability, Subject Relevance, Secondary Education, Imo State Schools

Introduction

Education remains a catalyst for all round human modification. Be it socially, politically, economically, religiously and culturally. The outcome of acquiring education is far beyond the four walls of the school system. It has been proven to be expensive but the returns far exceeds the cost. No form of education leaves anyone neutral, as such there are behaviour modifications which to a large extent enables man become innovative and creative. The human mind at this point is channeled towards making meaning in a world where changes are on the increase on a daily basis. No amount of knowledge is too big or heavy for the human mind not to assimilate. Beyond the traditional approach where students' are formally orientated on issues for personal profiting, education creates avenue for other extra-curricular activities that may be of immeasurable benefits not just to students' alone. Such area may be considered as one of the most thriving areas locally if not globally. This area is regarded as the vocational aspect of education. Student's interest is the predisposition a student show why they are learning or being taught, which extends to the level of motivation they have to learn and progress in their education. It is the willful engagement of a student in a specific task or subject.

It is one area that presents students with alternative choice of being relevant not just to themselves alone but also the society in general. Vocational education is the practical aspect of education where students are exposed to craftworks with the help of an instructor. It has tipped to be viable in the sense that students find it interesting because it helps to bring out their innate qualities. In bringing this to light, the education settings birthed this vocational education through courses like agricultural sciences, business studies, home economics, woodwork etc. which merely optional courses for students to undertake. In recent past like in Nigeria in the course of reviewing the curriculum collapsed most of the vocational education courses and made it compulsory for students from their junior secondary level and a must pass for them before the senior secondary school level of education a good example is the introduction of civic education.

According to Danko (2006) in defining vocational education lent his view on vocational education which he defined as any programme of specialized education designed to prepare individuals for entrance or additional training in specific occupation. In broader terms, vocational education is geared towards preparing students into various occupational fields for optimal and impactful effective participation, being responsible citizens, economically sound for sustainable development and a means to facilitating employment and poverty alleviation. Ngaloru (2012) contributed by defining vocational education as the study of technologies and related sciences, and the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge related to occupations and various sectors of economics and social life. Vocational education according to the definition suffice that aside from teaching students morals for meaningful living, being responsible and observing ethical rules and regulations provides students with practical knowledge through rigorous thinking and in return contributing in their own little way to economically productive ever growing system.

Statement of Problem

Good intentions do not in any way portrays good results. This is so because if for any reason government or non-governmental organization introduces vocational education for students, the likely possibility that it will thrive is very slim. This does not mean that motive is wrong or fruitless. There may be some unraveled factors which may hinder it from seeing the light of the day. Globally, international economies do experience ups and downs in its transaction on a regular basis. The only challenge is locating these challenges and how to tackle them headlong. Vocational education may on its own be an escape route to certain

challenges since it is targeted at making students economically, socially, politically, religiously and culturally useful to the society. When students loose in interest in acquiring relevant of knowledge in a certain areas that would be of help to them it implies that certain logistics have not been put in proper place.

Acquiring relevant knowledge in vocational education is no doubt a good step in the right direction. The only barrier that may face this exercise is the absence of those leverage that may be necessary for the smooth running of vocational education exercise. Hence, the study sought to find out ways of managing students' interest in acquiring vocational skills in secondary schools in Imo state.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to investigate ways of managing students' interest in acquiring vocational skills in secondary schools in Imo State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. find out vocational subjects available for male and female in public senior secondary schools in Imo State
2. examine the relevance of vocational subjects for male and female in public senior secondary schools in Imo State

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What are the vocational subjects available in vocational subjects for male and female in public senior secondary schools in Imo State?
2. What are the relevance of vocational subjects to students for male and female in public senior secondary schools in Imo State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between mean score rating of female and male teachers on the vocational subjects available in vocational subjects in public senior secondary schools in Imo State.
2. There is no significant difference between mean score rating of female and male teachers on the relevance of vocational subjects to students in public senior secondary schools in Imo State.

Concept of Vocational Education

The term vocational education has been variously defined and interpreted by different scholars. The National Policy on Education maintained that vocational education is the form of education which is obtained at the technical college equivalent to the Senior Secondary Education but designed to acquire practical skills, basic scientific knowledge and attitude required as craftsmen and technicians at sub-professional level. This definition portrays vocational education as primarily concerned with the acquisition of practical skills. According to Ogoh (2008), Vocational education can also be viewed as vocational or technical training or retraining which is given in schools or classes under public supervision and control and which are designed to fit individuals for gainful employment in recognized occupations as semi-skilled workers or technicians or sub-professionals. Ogoh explained that vocational education is designed to prepare individuals for employment in occupations which

require specialized training excluding those that are considered professional and which require a bachelor's degree.

Here, vocational education is seen as that part of general education aimed at developing skills and competencies needed to function effectively in any occupation or cluster of occupations. Contextually, vocational education is therefore considered as that part of the general education curriculum that is primarily concerned with the inculcation of practical skills, attitudes and knowledge necessary for self-reliance or for securing and sustaining employment in a given occupation or cluster of occupation. Vocational education and training is the process of teaching skills or knowledge that is necessary for particular job (Hornby, 2008).

Also Tsang (1997) stated that vocational education and training is any type of job related learning that raises an individual's productivity. It includes the learning in formal vocational education and technical school programmes, located in training centres, institutes and in the work place. According to the United Nations Education, Science and Culture Organization (UNESCO, 2004) Vocational education and training is regarded as an effective tool for achieving social cohesion, integration and self-esteem. This calls for a need to ensure that vocational education and training systems are developed and strengthened to provide appropriate opportunities for the development and certification of skills relevant to the labour market (ILO, 2004).

Vocational Skill Subjects Available in Secondary Schools

Vocational education in Nigeria includes the following subjects: practical agriculture, basic technology, business studies, home economics, local crafts, computer education, cultural and creative arts, and music are taught at the secondary school level. At this level of education, emphasis is placed on exploratory experiences within the general education context. Vocational subjects are subjects in technology that seek to immerse students in technology through exploration. These subjects provides students with a process of orientation in production and consumption through experiences in planning, producing, testing, servicing and evaluating types of consumer and industrial goods. Though at the secondary schools, the level of vocational education is treated at it basic, primary and general knowledge as there are no higher experience or knowledge being taught the students to empower them meaningfully (Uwameiye & Onyewadume, 1999 in Okoye & Ogunleye, 2015).

The exposure of students to vocational subjects enables them to develop a wider understanding of industrial processes and helps them explore their individual interest and aptitudes. Students may develop desirable traits and attitudes, such as pride in productive work, and respect for authority through such exposure. The philosophy of vocationalism presupposes that the products of the Secondary School should be equipped with the capacity to be familiar with the world of work, career options and choices. FRN (2004) outlined the following as the objectives of vocational education in Nigeria:

- i. Provide basic pre-vocational orientation for further training in technology.
- ii. Provide basic technological literacy for everyday living.
- iii. Stimulate creativity and sustain interest.

The attainment of these objectives is capable of sustaining students' interest in vocational subjects and fostering enrolment into the Technical colleges and Technical and Vocational

Education programmes at the tertiary education level. The need for the educational system to be relevant to societal aspirations always influences curriculum change or innovations (Ijaiya, N. Y. S). Nigeria launched the present education curriculum in 2011 as a re-aligned curriculum designed to meet the target of the reforms in the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategies (NEEDS) and the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) (Okoye & Ogunleye, 2015). These targets are: value-orientation, poverty eradication, job creation, wealth generation and the empowerment of people through education (Okoye & Ogunleye, 2015). The new Senior Secondary Education Curriculum (SSEC), which builds on the Basic Education Curriculum (BEC), aims at preparing every student for higher education, equipping them with functional trade/entrepreneurship skills and strengthening their ethical, moral and civic values (Orji, 2012). Thirty-four Trade and Entrepreneurial subjects were designed to be incorporated into the restructured formal education curriculum in order to enable skill development (Okoye & Udodo, 2015; Orji, 2012; Okoye & Ogunleye, 2015; Adejuyigbe & Adejuyigbe, 2016). These subjects are:

1. Auto body repairs and spray painting
2. Auto Electrical work
3. Auto Mechanical works
4. Auto parts merchandising
5. Air-conditioning Refrigerator
6. Welding and Fabrication, engineering craft practice
7. Electrical Installation and Maintenance work
8. Radio, TV and Electrical work
9. Block laying, Bricklaying and Concrete work.
10. Painting and decorating
11. Plumbing and Pipe Fitting
12. Machine woodworking
13. Carpentry and Joinery
14. Furniture Making
15. Upholstery
16. Catering craft practice
17. Garment Making
18. Textile Trade
19. Dyeing and Bleaching
20. Printing Craft Practice
21. Cosmetology
22. Leather Goods Manufacturing and Repair
23. Keyboarding
24. Data Processing
25. Store Keeping
26. Book Keeping
27. GSM Maintenance
28. Photography
29. Tourism
30. Mining
31. Animal Husbandry
32. Fisheries
33. Marketing
34. Salesmanship

Students are required to offer and register one trade/entrepreneurial subject in which they will be assessed in a public examination such as NECO or WAEC (Orji, 2012). Schools are required to select vocational subjects based on the following considerations:

1. Type of school
2. Vision of the school
3. Teaching staff
4. School infrastructures
5. Community interest and support
6. Availability of local resources
7. Socio-cultural inclination among others (Orji, 2012).

Akram (2012) and Odu (2010) support the vocalisation of the senior secondary education curriculum. Akram (2012) posited that education can only become the foundation stone of a sustainable society if it succeeds in imparting necessary life skills, as vocalisation ensures that participants are equipped with skills, knowledge and aptitudes that enable them engage in productive work, adapt to rapidly changing labour markets and economies, and contribute in their respective societies as responsible citizens. Similarly, Odu (2010) stated that the introduction of vocational subjects into the curriculum was necessitated due to the fact that formal education did not meet the needs of a vastly increased youth population who require manual and technical skills for gainful employment. However Odu (2010) noted that vocalisation alone was not sufficient without proper and successful implementation of technical and vocational programmes in schools. Implementation is also not possible without a proper understanding of the attitudes of students and teachers towards vocational education.

Relevance of Vocational Skill Subjects in Secondary Schools

The practical know-how, scientific skills and knowledge are to make the recipient (individual) to be creative and productive in order to function as a performing member of the society. In essence the main goals of teaching technical and vocational education in Nigerian technical colleges are to prepare students for the world of work through the acquisition of theoretical and practical skills (FRN, 2004 as cited in Ali & Muhammad, 2012). This implies that; the technical institutions are expected to train and produce graduates who are equipped with the practical rudiments of their chosen trades.

The trades offered in the technical and vocational institutions include: Mechanical engineering trades, Electrical/electronic trades, Construction trades, Vocational trades such as Home economics, Fine and Applied Arts and Business trades (International Qualification Assessment Services, IQAS, 2011). It means therefore, that the rationale for training students in these trades is to impart or rather for the acquisition of knowledge, attitudes and practical skills that are marketable and lucrative for a sustainable development. Therefore, to impart these qualities in any individual effective teaching strategy or techniques must be employed during the teaching and learning process.

Pautler (2009) emphasises that students "at risk", that is; those who fail or are dropouts, could benefit from vocational education at secondary level. Vocational education should not, however, be seen as a dumping ground for these students. It is important for the average and the above average student. When the academic side of the curriculum has clearly prescribed problems, vocational education must be considered as a viable alternative. Pautler further states that vocational education is charged with preparing people for work. It constitutes the backbone of the nation's employment, relating education to training. Bennel (2011) puts

forward the objective of vocational education as the augmentation of the national reservoir of human resources available for economic development in order to facilitate job creation.

Lauglo and Lillis (1988) cite that the main objective of vocational education is to influence the occupational choices of pupils away from white collar jobs to which they have traditionally aspired, and to make them somewhat better prepared to work in other types of occupations. The major function of schooling is the development of appropriate skills and attitudes that are needed to make the economic system of society function more efficiently.

Corson (1988) distinguishes between two types of people: those who are able to cope with higher cognitive problems and those who are not. Those who cope academically apparently do not require vocational training. Vocational training is directed to those that are not able to cope with rational problems and cannot master cognitive skills. It also helps those who lack home support in the quest for university education. We need to take into cognizance of this when providing any type of education to the learners. That is why we cannot only provide academic education but also vocational skills.

Okoye and Udoudo (2015) stated that the acquisition of the appropriate practical skills that vocational education offers is a means by which the productive power of a nation can be increased, which will result in economic growth of the nation. UNESCO-UNEVOC explains that the development of practical skills results in the acquiring of socially and economically rewarding jobs and can help the development of small scale businesses, allow the return of displaced workers as well as aid the easy transition from school to the world of work for school leavers, dropouts and graduates. It further states that the development of job-related competencies and skills among the poor, youth and the vulnerable is vital to reducing poverty. Okoye and Udoudo (2015) reiterates this by stating that the empowerment of youths with these appropriate practical skills is essential to curb the increasing rate of social vices and ills and the negative repercussions of joblessness.

Vocational/technical education is designed to offer people the opportunity of improving themselves in their general proficiency, especially in relation to their present or future occupation. Nuru (2007) opined that changes in any nation's economy is required to prepare young people for the jobs of the future of which technical and vocational education have crucial roles to play.

Methodology

The design of this study was a descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised all the 296 public senior secondary schools in Imo State. The sample size for this study comprised 376 teachers drawn from the entire population using Taro Yamen's formula. A disproportionate stratified random sampling technique was used to draw 209 male and 167 female teachers in the 296 public senior secondary schools in Imo State. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled 'Availability and Relevance of Vocational Subjects for Male and Female Students in Public Secondary Schools Questionnaire (ARVSF MFSPSSQ). The instrument was subjected to scrutiny by supervisor in the field of Educational Management. The reliability of the instrument was obtained through a test re-test reliability test. This was done by the researcher administering 20 copies of the instrument to 20 teachers outside the study sample. After two weeks, the same process was repeated. The scores was correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient to determine the reliability index of 0.84 and 0.65. Therefore, the overall reliability index yielded 0.72. This indicated that the instrument was reliable. The data

collated from the respondents was presented in tables, and analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the two (2) research questions. z-test statistics was used also to test the two (2) hypotheses at 0.05 alpha levels of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question One: What are the vocational subjects available in vocational subjects in public senior secondary schools in Imo State?

Table 1: Mean ratings and standard deviation of Male and Female Teachers on Available Vocational Skills in Secondary Schools in Imo State.

S/N	Available Vocational Skills	Male Teachers = 203			Female Teachers = 162			
		\bar{x}_M	S. D _M	Remarks	\bar{x}_F	S. D _F	Rank Orde r	Remarks
1	Practical Agriculture	3.44	0.98	Agreed	2.84	1.09	2 nd	Agreed
2	Basic Technology	2.31	1.07	Disagreed	2.31	1.13	7 th	Disagreed
3	Business Studies	3.46	0.98	Agreed	3.22	1.11	1 st	Agreed
4	Home Economics	2.62	0.90	Agreed	2.70	1.27	5 th	Agreed
5	Local Craft	3.15	0.97	Agreed	2.79	1.05	4 th	Agreed
6	Cultural and Creative Art	3.22	0.49	Agreed	2.82	0.96	3 rd	Agreed
7	Computer	2.43	1.20	Disagreed	2.27	1.12	6 th	Disagreed
8	Music	2.08	0.49	Disagreed	1.49	0.92	8 th	Disagreed
	Average Mean/Std. Deviation	2.84	0.89	Agreed	2.56	1.08		Agreed

Source: Survey Data 2019

Table 1 shows the weighted mean and rank order scores of male and female teachers on the available vocational skills in secondary schools in Imo State, Nigeria. Eight questionnaire items addressed research question 2 which items 1, 3, 4, 5 and 6 were accepted as available vocational skills in secondary schools in Imo State as they had mean scores greater than the criterion mean of 2.50. While items 2, 7 and 8 were rejected as not part of the available vocational skills in secondary schools in Imo state, because their mean score is lower than the criterion mean of 2.50. On the ranking of available vocational skills in secondary schools in Imo State, Business studies came first, followed by practical agriculture, cultural and creative art, local craft, home economics, computer, basic technology and music with mean scores of 3.34, 3.14, 3.02, 2.97, 2.66, 2.35, 2.31 and 1.79 respectively.

Research Question Two: What is the relevance of vocational subjects to students in public senior secondary schools in Imo State?

Table 2: Mean ratings and standard deviation of Male and Female Teachers on Relevance of Vocational Skill Subject in Secondary Schools in Imo State.

S/N	Relevance of Vocational Skill Subject	Male Teachers = 203			Female Teachers = 162			
		\bar{x}_M	S. D _M	Remarks	\bar{x}_F	S. D _F	Rank Order	Remarks
9	Vocational skills make students to be creative.	3.30	1.12	Agreed	2.95	0.47	4 th	Agreed
10	Vocational skill is an alternative means of being gainfully employed in the future.	3.36	0.87	Agreed	3.39	0.53	2 nd	Agreed
11	It influences occupational choice of students.	3.22	0.71	Agreed	3.42	0.74	3 rd	Agreed
12	Vocational skills aid students to be economically productive.	3.55	0.89	Agreed	3.51	0.63	1 st	Agreed
	Average Mean/Std. Deviation	3.36	0.90	Agreed	3.32	0.60		Agreed

Source: Survey Data 2019

Table 2 shows the weighted mean and rank order scores of male and female teachers on the relevance of vocational skill subjects in secondary schools in Imo state, Nigeria. Four questionnaire items addressed research question 2 which all item were accepted as the relevance of vocational skill subjects in secondary schools in Imo state as they had mean scores greater than the criterion mean of 2.50. On the ranking of the relevance of vocational skill subjects in secondary schools in Imo state, item 12 came first, followed by items 10, 11 and 9 with mean scores of 3.53, 3.38, 3.32 and 3.13 respectively.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between mean score rating of female and male teachers on the available vocational skills in secondary schools in Imo State.

Table 3: z-test Analysis on the Difference between the Mean Scores of female and male teachers on the available vocational skills in secondary schools in Imo State, Nigeria.

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	S.D	df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Decision
Male Teachers	203	2.84	0.89	363	26.3	±1.96	Rejected
Female Teachers	162	2.56	1.08				

Table 3 shows that female teachers have mean and standard deviation scores of 2.84 and 0.89 while male have mean and standard deviation scores of 2.56 and 1.08 respectively. With a degree of freedom of 374 at an alpha level of 0.05, the calculated z-value of 26.33 is greater than the critical z-value of ±1.96. Therefore the null hypothesis was rejected. By

implications, there is a significant difference between the mean ratings of female teachers and male teachers on the available vocational skills in secondary schools in Imo State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between mean score rating of male and female teachers on the relevance of vocational skill subjects in secondary schools in Imo state.

Table 4: z-test Analysis on the Difference in the Mean Scores of Female and Male Teachers on the relevance of vocational skill subjects in secondary schools in Imo state, Nigeria.

Respondents	n	\bar{x}	S.D	df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Decision
Male Teachers	203	3.36	0.90	363	0.49	± 1.96	Accepted
Female Teachers	162	3.32	0.60				

Table 4 shows that female teachers have mean and standard deviation scores of 3.36 and 0.90 while male teachers have mean and standard deviation scores of 3.32 and 0.60 respectively. With a degree of freedom of 363 at an alpha level of 0.05, the calculated z-value of 0.49 is lesser than the critical z-value of ± 1.96 . Therefore the null hypothesis was accepted. By implications, there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of female and male teachers on the relevance of vocational skill subjects in secondary schools in Imo state, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Available Vocational Skills in Secondary Schools

The result of the second findings revealed that the available vocational skills in secondary schools in Imo State are practical agriculture, business studies, home economics, local craft, cultural and creative art. And there is a significant difference between the mean ratings of female teachers and male teachers on the available vocational skills in secondary schools in Imo State, Nigeria when subjected to z-test. This finding is in line with Orji, (2012) who states that the new Senior Secondary Education Curriculum (SSEC), which builds on the Basic Education Curriculum (BEC) was aimed at preparing every student for higher education, equipping them with functional trade/entrepreneurship skills and strengthening their ethical, moral and civic values. Okoye and Udouo, (2015); and Adejuyigbe and Adejuyigbe, (2016) concurred to the above when they noted that thirty-four Trade and Entrepreneurial subjects were designed to be incorporated into the restructured formal education curriculum of secondary schools in order to enable skill development. According to the scholars above, these subjects are: Agricultural works, Auto body repairs and spray painting; Auto Electrical work; Auto Mechanical works; Auto parts merchandising; Air-conditioning Refrigerator; Welding and Fabrication, engineering craft practice; Electrical Installation and; Maintenance work; Radio, TV and Electrical work; Block laying, Bricklaying and Concrete work; Painting and decorating; Plumbing and Pipe Fitting; Machine woodworking; Carpentry and Joinery; Furniture Making; Upholstery; Catering craft practice; Garment Making; Textile Trade; Dyeing and Bleaching; Printing Craft Practice; Cosmetology; Leather Goods Manufacturing and Repair; Keyboarding; Data Processing;

Store Keeping; Book Keeping; GSM Maintenance; Photography; Tourism; Mining; Animal Husbandry; Fisheries; Marketing and Salesmanship.

Relevance of Vocational Skill Subjects in Secondary Schools

The third finding revealed that the relevance of vocational skill subjects in secondary schools in Imo state is that; it makes students to be creative; it is an alternative means of being gainfully employed in the future; it influence occupational choice of students; and aid students to be economically productive. Also, the z-test revealed that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of female and male teachers on the relevance of vocational skill subjects in secondary schools in Imo state, Nigeria.

This finding is in consonance with National Policy of Education (FRN, 2004) as cited in Ali and Muhammad, (2012) that practical know-how, scientific skills and knowledge are to make the recipient (individual) to be creative and productive in order to function as a performing member of the society. In essence the main goals of teaching technical and vocational education in Nigerian technical colleges are to prepare students for the world of work through the acquisition of theoretical and practical skills. This implies that; the technical institutions are expected to train and produce graduates who are equipped with the practical rudiments of their chosen trades. The finding is also in line with Pautler (2009) who emphasizes that students are "at risk", that is; those who fail or are dropouts, and could not benefit from vocational education at secondary level. Pautler further states that vocational education is charged with preparing people for work. It constitutes the backbone of the nation's employment, relating education to training. Bennel (2011) puts forward the objective of vocational education as the augmentation of the national reservoir of human resources available for economic development in order to facilitate job creation.

In agreement with the above, Okoye and Udoudo (2015) stated that the acquisition of the appropriate practical skills that vocational education offers is a means by which the productive power of a nation can be increased, which will result in economic growth of the nation. Okoye and Udoudo (2015) reiterates this by stating that the empowerment of youths with these appropriate practical skills is essential to curb the increasing rate of social vices and ills and the negative repercussions of joblessness.

Conclusion

Based on findings, this study concludes that vocational skills taught at the secondary school level in Imo State, empower students to be creative; it serves as alternative means of being gainfully employed in the future.

Recommendations

Based on the study findings, the following are hereby recommended:

1. The government should come up with plans and innovations to enhance the available vocational skills in secondary schools.
2. The school management and the government should see the need to explore every benefits that vocational skill offer, owing to the fact that the relevance of vocational skill to the students is essential especially in the face of rising unemployment rate in the country.

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